

The use of Marine Autonomous Systems in Ocean observation under the LOSC: Maintaining access to and sharing benefits for Coastal States

Abstract:

The increasing use of marine autonomous systems (MAS) in ocean observation has improved the speed and quality of data collected. However, it is unclear whether the existing legal framework remains fit for purpose to regulate the employment of MAS used in ocean observation. The chapter uses the framework governing marine scientific research (MSR) under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (LOSC) as a yardstick to assess challenges for implementing the laws deriving from the use of MAS in sustained and experimental ocean observation. Such a framework attempts to maintain a balance between the principle of freedom and the jurisdiction of coastal States. It also seeks to strengthen the scientific and technological capacities of developing States. The chapter argues that regulatory instruments from competent International Organisations and current practices of States and competent International Organisations with respect to the use of MAS in MSR projects are setting subsequent practices and agreements for interpreting the LOSC in light of technological advances of the 21st century, keeping the balance envisioned by negotiators of strengthening developing countries' marine sciences and technological capacities.

Key words: marine autonomous system, ocean observation, marine scientific research, benefit sharing, consent regime, duty to cooperate.

Introduction

Marine autonomous systems (MAS) have been used in ocean observation providing purposeful data in expedited time (Moltmann et al., 2019). In a recent example, tsunami warnings following the eruption of the volcano *Hunga Tonga-Hunga Ha'apai* prevented deadly consequences (NOAA, 2022). However, one might question the need for dedicated legislation regulating the use of MAS (Bax et al., 2018).

This chapter responds to such an inquiry by analysing whether the framework governing marine scientific research (MSR) under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (LOSC or Convention) could be a purposeful benchmark to regulate the use of MAS in ocean observation. It starts by examining operational aspects of MAS deployed in ocean observation, then revising elements of the framework governing MSR under LOSC, and finally analysing if and how to reconcile such framework and the use of MAS.

Ocean observation refers to activities evaluating elements of the physical environment in the ocean space. Sustained observations are measurements taken on an ongoing basis for seven years or more, primarily serving the public good services but also supporting research in the public interest (Cravatte et al., 2016, p. 4). Experimental observations are measurements taken for generally less than seven years for research and development purposes; serving to advance knowledge on the physical environment and climate, exploring technical innovation and/or leading to improvements in the effectiveness and efficiency of observing system programmes (Ibid).

With the absent definition for MSR in the LOSC, States and scholars diverge on classifying ocean observation as MSR (Huh/Nishimoto, 2017a; Mateos & Gorina-Ysern, 2010; Wegelein, 2005). De facto,

the LOSC framework governing MSR does not conflict with ocean observation, the reason why the former could serve as a yardstick for the latter.

MAS is an umbrella term not codified by law used by the oceanographic community. It encompasses the six models of carriers of sensors discussed here. Several studies have examined the status of MAS (Bork et al., 2008; Hofmann & Proelss, 2015; Veal et al., 2019), with significance for military uses, and ethical implications (Gorina-Ysern, 2003; Gorina-Ysern & Tsamenyi, 1997; Johansson, 2018). These have been followed by concerns over safety and risk to the marine environment (Klein et al., 2020). Less noticed, taking the MSR framework as a benchmark, the use of MAS might be detrimental to meeting the benefit-sharing obligations. This is of relevance since the existence of outstanding obligations justifies coastal States’ denial of permission for future research projects in their waters.

The chapter’s findings are supported by documentary analysis, perspectives substantiated by one of the author’s experiences managing scientific programs by the National Oceanographic Centre in the UK and views from researchers in the field. The study focuses on MAS applied for scientific and peaceful purposes, excluding those with commercial, military, or defence applications. It only considers research sponsored and promoted by States, and competent IOs, excluding privately funded, philanthropic, and citizen science MSR.¹

Operational Aspects of MAS employed in Ocean Observation

This section examines six types of MAS determining in each case the measurements, potential sensors, the capability of being launched, piloted and recovered independently of a mothership, and range of modus operandi and autonomy (IMO, 2021).

Table 1 Degrees of autonomy proposed by the International Maritime Organisation

Degree	Description
D1	Ship with automated processes and decision support. Some operations may be automated and unsupervised but with seafarers on board ready to operate and control shipboard systems and functions.
D2	Remotely controlled ship with seafarers on board. The ship is controlled and operated from another location. Seafarers are available onboard to take control and operate the shipboard systems and functions.
D3	Remotely controlled ship without seafarers on board. The ship is controlled and operated from another location. There are no seafarers on board.
D4	Fully autonomous ship: The operating system of the ship is able to make decisions and determine actions by itself.

Source: Prepared by the authors

Marine Autonomous Surface Ship (MASS)²

MASS have a length overall (LOA) ranging from 1m to 5m; some operated by commercial survey companies may have up to 70m. They are a mix of in-house and commercially produced MASS which

¹ Competent International organisations are those whose mandate include coordinating and promoting MSR, including those listed in Annex VIII, LOSC (OALOS, 1991, p. 1).

² See:

<https://noc.ac.uk/facilities/marine-autonomous-robotic-systems/asv>

can be deployed for months. Their power sources include solar, wave, wind, hybrid fuel cells and traditional marine engines. They are fitted with passive and active sensors covering measurements of meteorological, oceanographic, biological, photographic, and acoustic parameters. Some can deploy and recover other MAS such as UUVs and ROV's (AutoNaut, 2020).

MASS have been launched and/or recovered from mother ships, researching States, coastal States, third-party States, or combinations thereof. The piloting has taken place on mother vessels and/or remote piloting centres located in researching States, coastal States, third-party States or a combination. They are controlled using satellite communications with access to the data collected via the same capability and tracked using AIS. Measured data is saved onboard the MASS.

They can be operated at autonomy level D4 but are commonly controlled at D3 level.

Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUV)³

UUVs are either electric-powered, classed as Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV), or use buoyancy engines, classed as gliders.

UUVs are a mix of in-house and commercially produced capabilities with sizes varying between man-portable to 10m. They are fitted with passive and active sensors covering measurements of oceanographic, biological, chemical, optical - including imagery - and acoustic parameters. UUVs have been deployed on experimental observations lasting from one day up to several months, from shallow waters > 50m down to full ocean depth.

UUVs have been launched and/or recovered from mother ships, researching States, coastal States, third-party States or a combination. The piloting has taken place on mother vessels and/or remote piloting centres located in researching States, coastal States and third-party States or a combination. When on the surface, they are controlled using satellite communications with access to the data collected via the same capability and tracked by AIS. When submerged, they run on pre-programmed tracks and depths. Measured data is saved onboard.

UUVs are operated at autonomy level D4 when submerged and at level D3 when on the surface and when underwater acoustic telemetry is available.

Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV)⁴

ROVs are generally commercially purchased, but some marine research institutes build in house vehicles. Their sizes vary from man-portable to those requiring specialised containers for transport and bespoke launch and recovery gantries. They are operated down to full ocean depth with an average of 6000m and are fitted with passive and active sensors covering measurements of oceanographic, biological, chemical, optical - including imagery - and acoustic parameters.

³ For examples of AUV, see: <https://noc.ac.uk/facilities/marine-autonomous-robotic-systems/autosubs>. For examples of gliders, see: <https://noc.ac.uk/facilities/marine-autonomous-robotic-systems/gliders>

⁴ See: <https://noc.ac.uk/facilities/marine-autonomous-robotic-systems/deep-platforms>

ROVs have been launched, recovered and operated from mother ships, although they can be launched and recovered from MASS (Ocean Infinity, 2020). The piloting is undertaken from remote centres in researching States, coastal States and third-party States or a combination.

ROVs are normally operated at autonomy level D3.

Profiling Floats (PF)⁵

PF are fitted with sensors covering the measurement of oceanographic, biological and chemical parameters. Most PF are commercial products. Recent developments have seen floats capable of being operated down to 4000m. They are carried along by ocean currents, and are not recovered.

PF are launched from research vessels and ships of opportunity. There have been trials of both air-launched PF and from MASS. The piloting is remote and can be undertaken from centres in researching States, coastal States and third-party States or a combination. When on the surface, they are controlled using satellite communications with access to the data collected via the same capability and tracked using AIS. When submerged, they run on pre-programmed depths.

The level of autonomy for PF of all types is D3.

Seabed Observatory (SO)⁶

SOs come in many forms, from a buoyed system as with the Porcupine Abyssal Plain (PAP) example through to fixed submerged seabed structures. In general, they are produced in house by the research institutes with bespoke capabilities. SOs can be found both in shallow water as well as in the deep ocean and are operated down to full ocean depth, running pre-programmed depths. They are fitted with passive and active sensors covering the measurement of oceanographic, biological, chemical, optical and acoustic parameters.

SOs can be long term installations that are serviced by research vessels. Observatories on the sea bed either store the data onboard, which is recovered when serviced, or give real-time access when cabled to a shore-based receiving station. SOs like the PAP are controlled using satellite communications with access to the data collected via the same capability from the surface part of the observatory.

They are primarily operated at autonomy level D4 but at times work the D3 level.

Remotely Piloted Aircraft (RPA)⁷

RPA can either be propeller powered fixed wing or rotary wing. Most RPAs are man-portable though there are large ones that require special launch and recovery capabilities (Air-Sea Interaction Laboratory, n.d.). They are fitted with passive and active sensors covering the in-air measurement of optical in a broad range of the spectrum, like temperature and meteorological parameters (Ridge and Johnson, 2020).

⁵ For examples of ARGO PF, see: <https://argo.ucsd.edu/>.

⁶ See: <https://projects.noc.ac.uk/pap/>

⁷ The acronym RPA is synonymous with Unmanned Air Vehicle.

RPA have been launched and/or recovered from mother ships, researching States, coastal States, third-party States or a combination. They use radio frequency communications for both piloting and data transfer. Backups of the data and operating parameters are stored onboard.

Shipborne and land-based RPAs are operated at an equivalent of autonomy level D3.

Legal Aspects of Using MAS in Ocean Observation

The LOSC provides a comprehensive framework governing MSR undertaken by States and/or competent IOs using vessels, installations, and equipment (Papanicolopulu, 2017b, p. 1733). The Convention’s MSR regulation is mostly located in Part XIII, which seeks to strike a balance between freedom and the jurisdiction of States (Gorina-Ysern, 2003; Soons, 1982).⁸ In areas under national jurisdiction (AUNJ) and international cooperation, the regulation also aims at strengthening developing States’ capacities in marine sciences by requiring the share of benefits accrued from MSR (Coelho, 2022; Salpin, 2013; von Kries et al., 2015).

The non-monetary benefits target the cluster of capabilities explained in table 2:

Table 2 Modalities of benefits (considered for this study)

		Articles
Training and Capacity Building 	Consent regimes	
	Participate on board of vessels, craft, or installations	249(1)(a)
	Receive support to assess and interpret data, samples, and information	249(1)(d)
	International cooperation	
	Training and capacity development	244(2)
	Create favourable conditions for MSR and integrate the efforts of scientists	243
	Strengthening MSR capabilities of developing States	244(2)
	Provide training and education for developing States	268(d)
	Promote the exchange of scientists and experts	269(c)
Access to Data, Samples, Information and Knowledge 	Consent regimes	
	Access data, samples, information, and knowledge	249(1)(b)(c)
	International cooperation	
	Promote the flow of data and information, including about health, safety of persons and the marine environment	242(2)
	Disseminate proposed major programs and their objectives	244(1)
Enable Research Infrastructure 	Facilitate the acquisition, evaluation and dissemination of marine technological knowledge, information and data	268(a)
	International cooperation	
	Development of marine technology and technological infrastructure	268(b)(c)
	Establishment and strengthening of national and regional marine scientific and technological research centres	275-276
	Consent regimes	

⁸ Jurisdiction with regards to MSR refers here to spaces in which international law attribute sovereignty, sovereign rights and jurisdiction to coastal States.

Establish Legal and Policy Framework 	Establishment of guidelines to assist in ascertaining the nature and implications of MSR	251
	International cooperation	
	Elaborating agreements to create favourable conditions for MSR	243
	Conclude contracts and agreements under equitable and reasonable conditions for the acquisition of marine technology	269(b)
	Establish guidelines for the transfer of marine technology	271

Source: Prepared by the authors, based on (Coelho, 2022; Harden-Davies & Snelgrove, 2020)

The rights and obligations related to such benefits differ in each maritime space and whether the research is under the consent regimes or international cooperation.

The Consent Regimes for MSR

The consent regimes are a degree of rights and obligations of coastal vis-à-vis researching States and competent IOs varying in each maritime AUNJ. Benefit-sharing obligations are tied in with the coastal states' rights to withhold clearance for a project. In internal waters, territorial sea, and archipelagic waters, coastal States have the discretion to deny consent and request any benefit, including monetary (Huh/Nishimoto, 2017b, p. 1648; Salpin, 2013).

In the EEZ and on the continental shelf, coastal States must grant clearance in normal circumstances whereas researching States and IOs must comply with post-cruise obligations under article 249 (Huh/Nishimoto, 2017b, p. 1681). These obligations have the twofold purpose of confirming the bona fides of the MSR project and of sharing benefits (Coelho, 2022). Coastal States only have a wider margin of discretion to withhold consent and impose additional compliance measures in a limited number of circumstances.

Stemming from the rights under articles 60 and 80, the first circumstance is when the MSR project involves the construction, operation, or use of artificial islands, installations, and structures (article 246(5)(c)). Another is when the project is of direct significance for the exploration and exploitation of marine resources.⁹ Alternatively, the research permission might be granted, followed by a request to restrict the public availability of the results (article 249(2)). Consent may also be denied when the project involves drilling into the continental shelf or introducing harmful substances into the marine environment (article 246(5)(b)). The last situation relates to a previous research which failed to comply with the duty to inform the nature and objectives of a given MSR project or with the post-cruise obligations.

International Cooperation

The duty to cooperate with the objective of increasing knowledge of the marine environment is applicable in all maritime zones. States and competent IOs are free to negotiate how to facilitate the clearance process as far as the research project has peaceful aims, respects the sovereignty, sovereign rights, and jurisdiction of States and mutually benefits all participants (article 242).

⁹ 'Direct significance' refers to research findings expected to enable locating, assessing, and monitoring of the status and commercial availability of resources (DOALOS, 2010, p. 10).

IOs have been key in creating favourable conditions for MSR and enhancing capacities. However, the participation of developing countries in international collaborations still is asymmetrical (IOC-UNESCO, 2020; Tolochko & Vadrot, 2021). The use of MAS could improve their participation, as such systems are usually cheaper to purchase and maintain. However, this is not without questioning the shortcomings of the LOSC to regulate the employment of MAS.

Using MAS and Maintaining the Balance Envisioned by the Framework on MSR

The LOSC is a product of its time (Buga, 2015). Nevertheless, it is considered a “living instrument” with the flexibility to accommodate changing circumstances either through interpretation (Heidar, 2020; McLaughlin, 2020) or subsequent practice (Buga, 2015). This section analyses if and how the MSR’s framework might regulate the use of MAS preserving the balance between States, including sharing benefits with coastal States. It examines potential incompatibilities between aspects of MAS and the legal framework proposing interpretative guidance. After, it assesses the informal contribution of non-binding instruments to advance interpretation and implementation. Lastly, it explores two cases in which MAS were employed in ocean observation and benefits were shared.

Evolutionary Interpretation of Part XIII

In AUNJ, the use of MAS in MSR and ocean observation potentially causes loopholes related to the three main aspects explored in the following.

When Coastal State Consent is needed

The status of a given MAS is relevant to determining the need for coastal States’ consent. MAS are generally classified as a vessel, installation, structure, platform, device, equipment, or craft, which are terms not defined in the LOSC (Veal et al., 2019). It behoves to national laws establishing which MAS are considered vessels (Veal et al., 2019; Wegelein, 2005). Installations are larger devices mobile or fixed, consisting of an assemblage of parts, some with the capability of manning, employed with the purpose of remaining in place for longer periods. This terminology includes structure and platforms (Hofmann & Proelss, 2015; Wegelein, 2005, pp. 138–235). Equipment, which includes crafts and devices, are smaller instruments, employed for a specific purpose and a short period (Hofmann & Proelss, 2015; Veal et al., 2019; Wegelein, 2005, p. 137). “Device” is also used when no other classification is applicable (Veal et al., 2019).

When the system is deployed from a mother vessel, the clearance process is connected to the vessel (Ibid, p. 32). Conversely, when deployed from shore or a platform without status of vessel, it has an autonomous status, like a “ship in its own right” (Ibid p. 32), what could trigger the need for consent to each MAS. Communication through official channels or between scientists from the States concerned could be useful to expedite the clearance process (article 250). Article 247 also provides a viable solution, facilitating authorization when the MSR project is under the auspices of competent IOs in the EEZ or on the continental shelf of a State member.

The project’s geographical location and the MAS expected date of first appearance and departure play a role in assessing when consent must be requested. It is indisputable that it is needed when the State in which the device transits coincides with that overseeing the location of data gathering. A diverse situation takes place when they are different.

In the territorial sea, archipelagic waters, or straits used for navigation of a third State, if considered vessels by national laws, a MAS would be entitled to the right of innocent or transit passage (articles 17, 52, and 38). The latter is also applicable to RPAs (article 38). In this case, the MAS would have to comply with national laws and regulations (article 21), refrain from carrying out research during the passage (articles 19(j), 40 and 54), and navigate on the surface and show the identification of the State of registry when an underwater vehicle (article 20). If not qualifying as a vessel, the MAS unlikely is entitled to innocent passage, potentially necessitating permission from third States when transiting (Veal et al., 2019, p. 33; Wegelein, 2005, p. 135).

In the EEZ and on the continental shelf, the principle of freedom of navigation prevails. However, it is uncertain whether the project's geographical location and the date of first appearance and departure, which must be informed in the pre-cruise phase, include just the site of data collection or also areas of transiting (article 248(c)(d)). Again, national laws must clarify this issue (article 246(1)), which can create a troublesome situation in projects involving multiple States. As a default, researching States should inform third States of MAS passing through their EEZs and continental shelves.

When the Consent for MSR can be Withhold by Coastal States

The status of MAS and the types of measurements supported by each technology are significant to recognise as likely circumstances under which coastal States have the discretion to withhold consent and request compliance with obligations other than those prescribed by article 249.

In the territorial sea, coastal States have the exclusive right to grant consent for MSR and the discretion to impose requirements, including the sharing of monetary benefits. Conversely, in the EEZ and on the continental shelf, coastal States have limited discretion to deny clearance to MSR projects. One example is when the activity involves the deployment of installations and structures. Interestingly, such discretion is not extensive to projects using equipment (Papanicolopulu, 2017b, p. 1735).

Notwithstanding the guidance provided before, the assessment criteria to classify a system as installation or equipment is rather subjective because there is no threshold for the system's size and time of employment. For instance, the extended range of time in which MASS and UUV can stay at sea could cast doubts on their classification as equipment. More clarity on the legal criteria to determine the status of each MAS would be helpful. In the meantime, communication between official channels or scientists would be useful to fill this gap.

Coastal States' discretion to withhold consent is also applicable if the MSR has economic significance. At first glimpse, this would not be the case for ocean observation, however, many of the parameters measured by the systems discussed can have commercial applications. Therefore, pre-cruise information should certify, beyond doubt, the nature of the research.

How to comply with the Benefit Sharing Obligations under Part XIII

Obligations from whichever source of international law usually require an action or omission, and sometimes the achievement of a result (ILC, 2001, p. 55, para. 3). Since the distinction between obligations of conduct and result is not exclusive (Ibid, p. 56, para. 11), an assessment of articles 242-

244 and 249 in light of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties and the doctrine of obligations provides a nuanced perspective.

Articles 242-244 establish goal-oriented obligations, which necessitate a permanent evolution leading to a particular 'defined or definable' outcome, even if no specific deadline exists (Wolfrum, 2011, p. 376). Consequently, cooperation concerning MSR should be continued and address asymmetric capacities and shared challenges. Furthermore, the format to accomplish such obligations' goals is of less relevance, allowing to accommodate MAS features.

In article 249, researching States and/or IOs sponsoring research bear responsibility for pre-cruise information and complying with post-cruise obligations, even if the activity is actually undertaken by a research institute. When such an institute is not a governmental entity, one could refer to parallel responsibilities for States and private persons (Wolfrum, 2011). In this case, while the formers must ensure that the latter behave in a certain way (Ibid, p. 379), research centres are responsible through State Parties for adopting certain actions (DOALOS, 2010), some of which constitute benefits.

To meet their duties, researching States and IOs should adopt the necessary steps, like enacting internal laws, and procedures compelling compliance with post-cruise obligations and monitoring enforcement. But, they are not legally required to ensure the obtainment of a result (Wolfrum, 2011). This conclusion is confirmed by the language used in article 249 which limits compliance to 'when practicable,' 'as soon as practicable,' and when requested by coastal States; or uses the vague obligation of 'undertake to provide' (article 249(1)(c)). However, since consent can be withheld due to outstanding obligations from a prior project, it is on researching States' interest to compel research institutes to fulfil their obligations.

Valuable opportunities for training and capacity building come out of the right to participate in the MSR project onboard research vessels, installations or equipment, particularly because not all States have access to research vessels and state-of-the-art technology (IOC-UNESCO, 2020). In the absence of capacity to carry crew in many MAS, the participation can take place in piloting centres, developing human capacities to build in-house systems or training in assessing and analysing data.

The use of MAS might not affect the duty to provide access to data, samples, information, and knowledge, because data collected from MAS is usually stored onboard and can be processed and shared soon after its collection. In the case of SO, data can be accessed in real-time. When required, researching States should be prompt to filter any data bearing economic significance for coastal States.

Informal Law-making Instruments

This subsection explores soft law and self-regulatory instruments alike adopted by IOs and private entities which, despite missing binding force, generally "announce and reflect eras of change and are often harbingers of legal progression" (Friedrich, 2010).

International Organisations

Seeking to induce the implementation of Part XIII, the United Nations Division for Ocean Affairs & Law of the Sea (DOALOS) published a guide in 1991, revised in 2010. Both editions draw attention to the

clearance procedure and consultation between scientists from involved States as relevant steps to build trust, expedite consent and share benefits (DOALOS, 2010, p. 28).

In the consent form, researching States must demonstrate the peaceful purpose of the project and its contribution to a body of knowledge, thus, differentiating it from prospection, exploration, and exploitation and attesting to its harmlessness to national security. Also, the adoption of measures to minimize impacts on the marine environment like risk assessment should be informed (Ibid, p. 40). Of relevance, the form template includes space to describe the systems used (Ibid p. 33). Conversely, Coastal States must inform the expected level of participation, the format in which the data should be provided, and the existence of ecological or culturally sensitive areas and areas-based management tools (ABMT) (Ibid, pp. 31, 42 and 45).

Involvement of local scientists in the early stages of the project can promote meaningful participation for developing States, and garner consensus on how to align the technicalities of MAS with the Part XIII's obligations (Ibid, pp. 29–32). It may also open opportunities for adding local, and regional areas of interest to the project proposal, incorporating traditional and local knowledge, promoting the optimal utilization of the information provided, and realize the transfer of technology (Bax et al., 2018). A similar approach has been adopted to discuss aspects of intellectual property rights (DOALOS, 2010, p. 32; Gorina-Ysern, 2003).

The Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO occupies a pivotal position in triggering cooperation and accommodating the MSR's framework to changing circumstances. It had an active role in drafting DOALOS guide and, in 2007, published a guideline on the procedure for MSR carried out by itself acting as a competent IO, according to article 247. Although never used, such guideline sets precedent for other IOs (GOOS 246, 2021, p. 23).

Private Sector

In compliance with the parallel obligations upon States and private entities, the scientific community adopted self-regulatory instruments seeking to minimize the environmental impact of MSR and assure safety standards (ISOM 2007; InterRidge 2009). The industry established codes of conduct reporting best practices for the deployment of MAS (UK 2018). States published guidelines informing scientific institutions how to conform to the LOSC requirements (UNLOS 2015, NOC 2019, SUT 2007). The latter exemplifies how States can improve the implementation of Part XIII by what McLaughlin (2020) calls conduciveness. However, the instruments consulted only discuss superficially the post-cruise obligations. The private sector should be more active in filling this gap.

Case Studies

The following cases exemplify MSR and ocean observation projects promoted by IO and States using MAS in which LOSC provisions on MSR were applied and benefits were shared.

Argo OceanOPS and ARGO Floats

The outputs of the ARGO array inform our long-term understanding of climate change and provide important inputs into ocean-atmosphere forecast models used for weather forecasting. Furthermore,

access to the observations in near real-time is open to all States even if they are not net providers of ARGO floats to the array.

The floats launched on the high seas are free to eventually drift into coastal States' waters. These unscheduled excursions into States EEZs have been seen by coastal States as unpermitted MSR. Such anomaly was addressed by IOC in 2008 via the adoption of a Guideline regulating the deployment of profiling floats in the High Seas within the framework of the Argo Programme (IOC Executive Council, 2008).

Member States of IOC agreed that coastal States concerned should be notified in advance of the deployment of floats with the potential entrance into their waters (Mateos & Gorina-Ysern, 2010). Besides, IOC and the World Meteorological Organisation act as clearing house mechanisms, receiving and releasing data collected in the public domain. IOC compromised to verify ways to maximize the number of States participating in the project and benefiting from it (IOC Assembly, n.d.). Coastal States have the right to retain the publication of data collected in their EEZs with economic significance (IOC Executive Council, 2008, Annex).

The data generated by the Argo Float Programme has been applied to education and capacity development by the Pacific Islands Applied Geoscience Commission (SOPAC), and by a partnership with the US in South America and Africa (Roemmich et al., 2009). Hence, through a soft-law instrument which resembles provisions of Part XIII, IOC member States adapted the rights and obligations to the respective features of floats, sharing benefits.

Commonwealth Marine Economies Programme (CMEP) Containerised Autonomous Marine Environmental Laboratory (CAMEL)

The CMEP and CAMEL serve as an example in which a State - the UK - undertakes MSR through MAS and meets its duty to promote access to and share the benefits of such activity with the respective coastal State.

The CMEP was launched in 2015 seeking to support the sustainable growth of Commonwealth SIDS by strengthening scientific and technological capacities thereupon to develop plans for environmental protection and designate ABMTs (UK, 2016; Ziegwied, 2019). CAMEL was developed and deployed as a project of CMEP aiming to expand the use of state-of-the-art technology, which is cheaper and easier to maintain than a traditional research vessel (Ziegwied, 2019). The facilities generally involve an operations container, a workshop, a C-Worker-4 Unmanned Surface Vehicle and an UUV ecoSUB, and three exchangeable sensor (Ibid). The capability covers oceanography, hydrography, marine meteorology, and marine environmental security measurements (Ibid). It also involves capacity development, since representatives of SIDS receive training on using the CAMEL system.

Between 2018 and 2019, CAMEL has already been successfully deployed for scientific data collection in Belize, contributing to investigating ocean acidification in shallow waters, including the Belizean Barrier Reef, with reduced costs compared with traditional methods of in situ investigation (Cryer et al., 2020). In 2019, it was used in Dominica, where CAMEL enabled producing marine habitat maps in support of two marine protected areas (NOC, n.d.).

In this case, bilateral agreements were capable to implement the obligations of conduct with respect to international cooperation achieving the required access to and benefits from MSR using MAS as laid out in Part XIII as well as transferring marine technology.

Conclusion

In wake of the LOSC's 40th anniversary, this study evidenced its contemporarily by demonstrating the framework's governing MSR suitability to serve as a benchmark regulating the use of MAS in ocean observation. The chapter examined situations in which the use of MAS challenges identifying when coastal States' consent is needed, when it can be withheld, and how to comply with benefit-sharing obligations, suggesting pathways to overcome such barriers. Furthermore, it assessed informal law-making processes advancing the Convention's flexibility to changing circumstances. The relevance of DOALO's guide and the work of IOC-UNESCO stood out in the analysis. The latter was a protagonist to establish a regulatory instrument, based on Part XIII, garnering consensus between divergent positions on the use of profiling floats. A second case evidenced how part XIII can inspire collaborations between States advancing the use of MAS in ocean observation and sharing benefits.

In preparation for the LOSC 50th birthday and aligned with the objectives of the Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, an update for the DOALOS Guide and a platform assembling IOC's best practices have been proposed (GOOS 246, 2021, p. 39). These exercises could be significant in fostering the implementation of Part XIII, considering new technologies, as well as improving developing countries' participation in marine sciences. The Argo Guidelines could inform discussions, particularly its notification system and the use of IOs as clearing house mechanisms. The guide's new edition should continue stressing the relevance of the consent form and official/direct communications between States involved to build trust and identify when consent is needed, how to avoid withholding it and to comply with the benefit-sharing obligations in light of new technologies. An expanded discussion on data sharing and property rights would also be beneficial. Besides, DOALOS and IOC could increase dialogue with sub-regional and regional organizations. The latter could assist States without the capability to process the consent request within the legal time frame, improving the internal legal and policy frameworks on MSR, and the enjoyment of the benefits accrued from MSR.

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